

Locating the Maldives in India's Foreign Policy Prerogatives

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Abstract: *This paper examines the strategic significance of the Maldives within India's foreign policy prerogatives, situating the bilateral relationship in the broader context of the Indian Ocean Region (IOR) and rising great-power competition. It argues that despite the Maldives' small size, its geographic location along critical sea lanes makes it central to India's maritime security and regional influence. Using a realist security framework, the study analyzes historical engagement, economic and defense cooperation, and recent political developments, including the 'India Out' campaign and the growing Chinese presence under the Belt and Road Initiative. The paper finds that while India has responded through renewed diplomatic, developmental, and security initiatives, its approach often remains reactive and insufficiently institutionalized. By foregrounding the agency of a small island state, the study contributes to debates on India's maritime strategy and highlights the need for a coherent, long-term engagement to sustain India's role as a key security provider in the IOR.*

Keywords: *India-Maldives, IOR, Maritime security, Realist Security Framework, China's Influence.*

Introduction:

Neighbouring states occupy a central place in the formulation of foreign policy, particularly for countries whose security and prosperity are closely tied to geography. For India, both land and maritime neighbours significantly shape its strategic environment. Stability in the immediate neighbourhood directly affects national security, economic development, and diplomatic standing. Consequently, India's foreign policy has consistently prioritized regional engagement, though the nature of this engagement has evolved over time.

In the early years after independence, India's regional approach was shaped by Jawaharlal Nehru's emphasis on non-alignment, peaceful coexistence, and moral leadership. This relatively idealistic orientation gradually gave way to a more pragmatic and security-driven approach as India confronted regional conflicts, internal challenges, and shifts in the global order. Economic liberalization and the rise of China further reinforced the need for strategic recalibration. By the twenty-first century, initiatives such as the 'Neighbourhood First' policy and SAGAR (Security and Growth for All in the Region) reflected India's attempt to combine development cooperation with security considerations, particularly in the maritime domain.

Within this evolving framework, the Maldives occupies a distinct position. Although small in size and population, its location in the heart of the Indian Ocean gives it strategic relevance disproportionate to its material capabilities. As competition intensifies in the IOR, understanding the Maldives' place in India's foreign policy is essential to assessing India's broader maritime strategy.

The Maldives in India's Foreign Policy: A Historical Overview

The Maldives is an archipelagic state comprising twenty-six atolls located roughly 700 kilometers from India's southwest coast. Its proximity to major international shipping routes that carry a substantial share of India's trade and energy imports makes it a critical maritime neighbour. Diplomatic relations between India and the Maldives were established in 1965, soon after Maldivian independence,

and have since been characterized by close political, cultural, and security ties.

A defining moment in bilateral relations occurred in 1988, when India intervened swiftly to foil a coup attempt in the Maldives. This intervention underscored India's role as a regional security provider and reinforced mutual trust. In subsequent decades, cooperation expanded to include defense training, infrastructure development, healthcare, education, and disaster relief. India played a key role in assisting the Maldives during the 2004 tsunami and has supported capacity-building in various civilian sectors.

However, Maldivian domestic politics have periodically altered the tone of bilateral relations. While phases of close alignment have strengthened cooperation, periods marked by nationalist rhetoric and concerns over sovereignty have generated friction. The shift from an 'India First' orientation to the 'India Out' narrative illustrates how internal political dynamics in the Maldives influence India's regional strategy.

Why Maldives Matters to India:

India's foreign policy towards the Maldives is strategically important due to geographic proximity, maritime security, and leverage in the Indian Ocean region.

The Maldives lies just 700 km from India's Lakshadweep Islands and approximately 1,200 km from the Indian mainland. This closeness places the Maldives directly within India's sphere of strategic interest. The island nation is located near major international sea lanes through which 80% of India's oil imports and nearly half of its trade cargo travel. Control or influence over this maritime zone thus becomes critical to India's economic and energy security.

As a maritime nation, India relies heavily on freedom of navigation and unimpeded maritime commerce. The Maldives plays a crucial role in this respect. It enables India to expand its surveillance and security coverage over the Indian Ocean. India has helped install coastal radar systems and provides regular defense training to Maldivian personnel. Moreover, India's presence in the Maldives helps counter non-traditional threats such as piracy, drug trafficking, and illegal fishing.

India aspires to be the regional leader in South Asia, and its engagement with smaller neighbours like the Maldives is a test of this ambition. By ensuring political stability, economic development, and strategic alignment in the Maldives, India seeks to project itself as a responsible and capable regional power. The Maldives, as a founding member of the SAARC and IORA (Indian Ocean Rim Association), provides India with valuable diplomatic support in multilateral forums.

The Maldives serves as a geopolitical hinge in India's maritime security architecture, an arena for strategic competition with China.

Why India Matters to Maldives:

From the Maldivian side too, India is equally important. India has consistently supported the Maldives' development through grants, concessional loans, and technical assistance. This support has facilitated various infrastructure projects, the construction of hospitals, water and sanitation initiatives, and ventures in renewable energy. The Maldivian economy, which relies significantly on tourism, has been bolstered by the influx of Indian tourists and investments. Furthermore, India has extended budgetary assistance during periods of economic difficulty, notably during the COVID-19 pandemic, by providing medical supplies, vaccines, and emergency aid.

Due to its limited domestic capacity, the Maldives relies on India for essential services. Maldivian citizens frequently travel to India for advanced medical treat-

ment, higher education, and skilled employment. Indian cities are seen as accessible and affordable destinations for Maldivians seeking quality healthcare and academic opportunities.

India has often supported the Maldives diplomatically in regional and international forums. When political transitions or instability have occurred in the Maldives, India has advocated for peaceful resolution and democratic processes. India's endorsement adds legitimacy to the Maldivian government on the global stage. Moreover, aligning with a regional power like India enables the Maldives to balance great power interests without being wholly dependent on any one country.

Importance of the Indian Ocean Region (IOR):

The Indian Ocean Region holds growing strategic, economic, and political significance in global affairs. The Indian Ocean, the third-largest ocean in the world, has emerged as a significant arena for geopolitical competition and cooperation. Its strategic location connects key regions of Asia, Africa, and the Middle East, making it a critical trade route. For India, which shares a vast maritime boundary with this region, the IOR is not only a natural sphere of influence but also a critical space that shapes its national security and foreign policy calculations.

The Indian Ocean is a critical region for global maritime trade, accounting for approximately 80% of the world's seaborne oil and over half of all container traffic. Key chokepoints, such as the Strait of Hormuz, Bab el-Mandeb, and the Strait of Malacca, render the Indian Ocean Region (IOR) vital to international commerce. For India, the significance of this region is particularly noteworthy, as a substantial percentage of its external trade and energy imports rely on the uninterrupted functioning of these maritime routes. Any disruption whether stemming from piracy, terrorism, or geopolitical rivalries could have serious implications for India's economic prosperity and energy security. As such, it is essential for India to actively engage in maritime security initiatives and collaborate with global partners to safeguard these critical trade corridors. India views the Indian Ocean as a vital extension of its strategic sphere, where establishing dominance or significant influence is integral to its aspirations of becoming a major global power.

By actively engaging in the Indian Ocean Region (IOR), India seeks to position itself as a net security provider, which is essential for promoting regional stability. Additionally, the IOR provides India with a platform to exercise strategic autonomy. The country collaborates with like-minded partners through established forums, such as the Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA), and participates in various Indo-Pacific frameworks. This multifaceted engagement enables India to diversify its partnerships and mitigate overreliance on any single global power, thereby strengthening its strategic flexibility on the international stage.

Theoretical Lens: Realist Security Framework:

To interpret India's engagement with the Maldives in its foreign policy prerogative, the realist school of international relations provides a particularly useful analytical lens. Realism, especially in its classical and structural variants, views the international system as anarchic and sees states as rational actors that prioritize survival, power, and national interest above all else. Security, both internal and external, becomes the most important concern in this theoretical tradition. Under realism, states are assumed to be the central actors in global politics. Their actions are guided not by ethical norms or international institutions, but by the pursuit of power and security in an unpredictable international environment.

Realists place high importance on geography. The Maldives's position near major Sea Lanes of Communication (SLOCs) makes it a geopolitical asset. Control over or alignment with maritime neighbours like the Maldives allows India to secure its trade routes and maintain regional naval superiority. Realism explains India's concerns over China's growing influence in the Maldives as a reaction to a perceived shift in the balance of power in the Indian Ocean region. The concept of realism offers an insightful perspective on the security dilemma, where an action taken by one state to enhance its security may be interpreted as a threat by other states. China's notable investments in infrastructure and its increasing political engagement in the Maldives have prompted India to strengthen its own presence in the region through strategic diplomacy, foreign aid, and defense partnerships. This ongoing balancing act exemplifies the realist principle of maintaining relative power in relation to potential rivals. Such dynamics illustrate the complexities inherent in international relations, particularly in competitive environments.

In recent years, China's entry into the Indian Ocean through its Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has caused strategic unease in New Delhi. Through port investments, debt diplomacy, and infrastructure funding, China has extended its influence in Sri Lanka, Pakistan, and increasingly in the Maldives. Under former President Abdulla Yameen's regime, the Maldives entered into several high-value agreements with Chinese firms, raising fears of a "debt trap" and potential Chinese military presence in India's immediate maritime vicinity.

The so-called "India Out" campaign, which gained momentum under the current pro-China leadership of President Mohamed Muizzu, further challenged India's traditional strategic comfort in the region. By capitalizing on nationalist sentiment and highlighting sovereignty concerns, the campaign has altered the public discourse around Indian military and developmental presence in the Maldives.

India's relationship with the Maldives is currently at a critical juncture. The dynamics of this small yet strategically significant island nation reflect the broader contestation in the Indian Ocean region between India's traditional influence and the assertive entry of external powers, especially China. While historical ties, economic cooperation, and geographic proximity continue to bind India and the Maldives, recent political shifts and strategic recalibrations have introduced new complexities into this bilateral equation.

Research problem:

In recent years, India's maritime neighbourhood has gained unprecedented strategic importance, particularly within the context of growing geopolitical contestation in the Indian Ocean Region (IOR). Among the island nations in the IOR, the Maldives occupies a critical position in both geographical and strategic terms. While India has historically enjoyed close ties with the Maldives, recent political shifts such as the "India Out" campaign and the strengthening of Maldives-China relations have raised questions about the effectiveness and adaptability of India's foreign policy in safeguarding its interests in its maritime neighbourhood. Despite being framed as a key partner under India's "Neighbourhood First" and "SAGAR" (Security and Growth for All in the Region) doctrines, the Maldives today appears to be increasingly leaning toward alternative alliances, prompting a reassessment of India's regional influence. This development highlights a pressing research gap: while India's continental neighbours have received significant scholarly and strategic attention, its maritime partners like the Maldives remain relatively under-theorized in foreign policy analysis.

This paper seeks to critically examine how and why the Maldives has become central to India's evolving foreign policy prerogative, particularly through the lens of realist security theory.

Literature Review:

Existing literature on India's foreign policy highlights its focus on the neighbourhood, but often overlooks the strategic significance of maritime partners like the Maldives.

Strategic Significance of the Maldives:

Maldives, strategically located in the Indian Ocean. Despite being the smallest South Asian nation, the Maldives holds significant importance due to its geographical position in crucial sea lines of communication. The Maldives is geographically positioned like a 'toll gate' between the western Indian Ocean chokepoints of the Gulf of Aden and the Strait of Hormuz on the one hand, and the eastern Indian Ocean chokepoint of the Strait of Malacca on the other (Kapoor, 2021). For India, the Maldives is central to its maritime security architecture and regional influence under frameworks such as the Neighbourhood First and SAGAR (Security and Growth for All in the Region) policies. China views the Maldives as a key node in its Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), specifically within the Maritime Silk Road. Through economic investments and infrastructure development, Beijing seeks to expand its strategic footprint in the Indian Ocean Region. Consequently, the Maldives has become a focal point in the emerging India-China maritime competition. The growing Chinese influence in the Maldives, consequent upon the planned or ongoing execution of a large number of Beijing-led investment projects, is a major concern for India (Kapoor, 2021).

India's Foreign Policy Challenge in the Maldives:

India has always been a reliable friend to the Maldives; in addition to saving the Gayoom regime in 1988, it helped the Maldives greatly during the tsunami disaster of 2004, the water crisis of 2013, and the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. Since 2007 the Maldives has also witnessed a tremendous change in its foreign policy from the 'India First' to the 'India Out' campaign. The "India First" policy of the Solih administration marked a positive turn in India-Maldives relations, but frequent political fluctuations in the Maldives create a strategic environment. India must engage more proactively, not only through economic aid and infrastructural support but also by building robust people-to-people ties and securing long-term defense cooperation agreements (Thakur, 2023). This challenge is compounded by China's ability to offer rapid and large-scale investments, often without the democratic or environmental accountability that Indian projects typically require.

China's Growing Presence in the Indian Ocean:

The Chinese naval warships made their first appearance in the Indian Ocean at the end of 1985. Much of the Western and Asian writing on China's Indian Ocean policy tends to focus on the growing Chinese dependence on energy and resource trade with the Indian Ocean littoral and the need to protect the vital sea lines of communication (Raja, 2012). China's assertive maritime policies and infrastructural investments have raised significant concerns for India. China's growing naval presence and strategic investments in key port infrastructure across the Indian Ocean—including Gwadar in Pakistan, Hambantota in Sri Lanka, Kyaukpyu port in Myanmar, and development projects in the Maldives—reflect a conscious attempt to establish a long-term maritime footprint (Butt and Siddiqui, 2021). The Maldives plays a central role in this framework. Its strategic location in the heart of

the Indian Ocean makes it a vital link in China's maritime strategy. Debt-driven investments in infrastructure and tourism have increased Chinese leverage over the island nation (Ahmad and Wagay, 2021). Through initiatives like the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and the so-called "String of Pearls" strategy, China seeks to enhance its access to critical sea lanes, extend its influence, and challenge the traditional dominance of regional powers like India.

Maritime Security and India's Naval Capabilities:

Maritime security is one of the major concerns and challenges for coastal countries. It is one of the biggest challenges of a country. The sea is an important factor for a country for different kinds of trade relations and other factors. The naval forces make strong policies and actions to secure maritime with their equipment and force. India's maritime strategy increasingly reflects concerns about its ability to maintain domain awareness and project power across the Indian Ocean. Despite possessing one of the largest navies in the region, India faces logistical and operational constraints when responding to fast-expanding Chinese maritime capabilities (Joy, 2020). Initiatives like SAGAR (Security and Growth for All in the Region), increased bilateral naval exercises, and the expansion of maritime domain awareness partnerships represent India's attempt to strengthen its maritime posture.

Growing Power Competition and Changing Regional Dynamics:

Recent studies describe the Indian Ocean as a space where major powers, especially India and China, are competing for influence. This competition is creating a major shift in the balance of power in the region, like a churning process that brings uncertainty and change. This includes not just military activities but also investment in ports, infrastructure, and stronger diplomatic ties with smaller countries like the Maldives (Raja, 2012). In 2017, China opened its first overseas military base in the Indian Ocean, in Djibouti. A growing Chinese presence across its diplomatic, political, and military footprint is certainly a cause for deep concern in Delhi. India already is in a tense and volatile situation with China along its northern continental border. A strong China in the Indian Ocean amplifies the Sino-Indian competition across land and maritime boundaries (Baruah, 2022).

Research Questions:

1. How and why is the Maldives central to India's foreign policy prerogative, and to what extent does India's current strategy reflect realist concerns of maritime security and regional influence?
2. How does the growing Chinese presence in the Maldives impact India's foreign policy choices?
3. Interpreting Chinese influence not just in terms of infrastructure but as a long-term maritime strategic challenge for India?

Methodology:

The methodology opted for this research is qualitative in nature and follows an analytical approach to study India's evolving foreign policy toward the Maldives. It relies primarily on secondary sources, including scholarly articles, policy papers, official documents, news reports, and think tank publications. These materials have been critically reviewed to trace historical developments, identify key turning points, and analyze patterns in India-Maldives relations.

The study is guided by the realist theory of international relations, particularly focusing on the concepts of security, strategic interest, and power projection. A historical-analytical method is used to examine India's policy from the Nehruvian

era to the present, while contemporary developments such as the “India Out” campaign and China’s strategic inroads are assessed through a geopolitical lens.

Key Findings:

This section presents the findings of the study in direct relation to the research questions and interprets them through a realist security framework. The analysis demonstrates that the Maldives occupies a strategically central position in India’s foreign policy, that China’s expanding presence has reshaped India’s policy responses, and that Chinese influence represents a long-term maritime strategic challenge rather than merely an economic engagement.

The findings indicate that the Maldives is central to India’s foreign policy prerogative primarily due to its strategic location in the Indian Ocean region and its proximity to critical sea lines of communication. From a realist perspective, India’s engagement with the Maldives is driven by concerns over maritime security, power projection, and regional influence rather than purely normative or developmental objectives. The Maldives’ location near vital shipping routes that carry a significant portion of India’s trade and energy imports makes it a key component of India’s maritime security architecture.

India’s current strategy reflects realist concerns to a considerable extent, particularly through defense cooperation, maritime surveillance support, and security assistance. Initiatives such as capacity building of the Maldivian defense forces and enhanced maritime domain awareness demonstrate India’s intent to prevent hostile powers from gaining strategic footholds in its immediate maritime neighbourhood. However, the findings also reveal that India’s approach lacks consistency and long-term institutionalization. Policy engagement often fluctuates in response to political changes within the Maldives, suggesting that while realist security concerns guide India’s actions, they are not always translated into a coherent and sustained strategy.

The study finds that China’s growing political, economic, and strategic presence in the Maldives has significantly influenced India’s foreign policy behavior. Chinese investments under the Belt and Road Initiative and expanding diplomatic engagement have altered the strategic landscape by offering the Maldives alternatives to Indian support. This has reduced India’s traditional leverage and compelled New Delhi to reassess its approach.

In response, India has adopted a more assertive and proactive foreign policy posture, characterized by increased financial assistance, accelerated infrastructure projects, and intensified naval diplomacy. From a realist standpoint, these actions represent balancing behavior aimed at maintaining India’s relative power position in the Indian Ocean Region. Rather than relying solely on historical ties, India has increasingly framed its engagement in strategic terms, emphasizing security cooperation and economic incentives. Nevertheless, the findings suggest that India’s responses are often reactive, shaped by immediate strategic concerns rather than long-term agenda-setting, which limits their effectiveness.

The analysis demonstrates that Chinese influence in the Maldives cannot be interpreted merely as infrastructure development or economic cooperation. Instead, it constitutes a long-term maritime strategic challenge for India. Chinese engagement creates the possibility of sustained political influence, strategic access to maritime spaces, and a potential future military presence in the Indian Ocean. From a realist perspective, this alters the balance of power in India’s immediate maritime environment and introduces a security dilemma for New Delhi.

The findings highlight that China's involvement enables the Maldives to diversify its foreign relations and exercise greater strategic autonomy, sometimes at the expense of India's traditional dominance. This shift increases India's strategic vulnerability, as even limited Chinese access in the Maldives could have disproportionate implications for India's maritime security. The study concludes that unless India moves beyond episodic responses and develops a comprehensive, long-term maritime strategy that integrates security, economic engagement, and diplomatic outreach, it risks a gradual erosion of its influence in the Indian Ocean Region.

Conclusion:

This study has examined the strategic importance of the Maldives within India's foreign policy prerogative, emphasizing how geographic proximity and maritime security concerns continue to shape bilateral relations. The Maldives occupies a critical position in India's Indian Ocean strategy, acting as both a security buffer and a partner in maintaining regional stability.

However, the increasing Chinese presence in the Maldives presents a complex challenge to India's traditional influence. The Maldives' shift towards China is driven by a combination of economic incentives, political calculations, and a desire for strategic autonomy, which India must carefully address through more consistent and multidimensional engagement. Applying a realist security framework, this paper argues that India's current strategy, though reflective of maritime security imperatives, requires greater coherence and sustained commitment. To maintain its leadership in the Indian Ocean Region, India must strengthen its diplomatic, economic, and cultural ties with the Maldives, moving beyond episodic responses to build a durable partnership. India's ability to effectively engage with the Maldives will be a key determinant of its broader regional influence and security posture in the years to come.

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